

Analytical Method Development and Validation of Gas Chromatographic Method for Residual Solvent Determination in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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Abstract

A robust and sensitive gas chromatographic (GC) method was developed and validated for the determination of residual solvents in esomeprazole, a proton pump inhibitor widely used in the treatment of acid-related gastrointestinal disorders. The method was designed in compliance with ICH Q3C and Q2(R1) guidelines for residual solvent analysis. Gas chromatography was performed using Capillary column, 30 m X 0.53 mm (DB 624) its temperature was 35°C maintain for 5 min, increase to 175 °C at a rate of 8°C/min then increase up to the 260 °C at a rate of 35°C/min maintain for 16 min. The Nitrogen Used as the carrier gas. The linear velocity carrier of 35cm/sec gas. The FID detector with the temperature up to 250°C. The method effectively separates and quantifies Class 2 and Class 3 solvents potentially present in the of esomeprazole. Method was developed and validate using parameters like specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantitation (LOQ), and robustness were evaluated. The method demonstrated excellent linearity over the concentration ranges tested. This validated GC method is suitable for routine quality control and regulatory compliance in pharmaceutical manufacturing of esomeprazole.

Keywords: Gas Chromatography, Esomeprazole, Validation, Residual Solvent

Introduction

Gas chromatography is a term used to describe the group of analytical separation techniques used to analyse volatile substances in the gas phase. In gas chromatography, the components of a sample are dissolved in a solvent and vaporized in order to separate the analyses by distributing the sample between two phases a stationary phase and a mobile phase. The mobile phase is a chemically inert gas that serves to carry the molecules of the analyte through the heated column. Gas chromatography is one of the sole forms of chromatography that does not utilize the mobile phase for interacting with the analyte. The stationary phase is either a solid adsorbant, termed gas-solid chromatography (GSC), or a liquid on an inert support, termed gas-liquid chromatography

(GLC). Residual solvents in pharmaceutical products are elucidated as organic volatile chemicals which are employed or may be formed during the manufacture process of drug substances or excipients, or during the process of preparation of drug products. The residual solvents don't seem to be utterly removed by practical manufacturing techniques. Appropriate choosing of the solvent for the synthesis of a drug substance or an excipient could help in the enhancement of the yield, or to determine the characteristics like crystal form, purity, and solubility^[1,2,3].

Figure 1: Esomeprazole

Materials and Methods

Reagents: Isopropyl alcohol, Dichloro methane, Dimethyl formamide.

Esomeprazole was obtained from Core Analyticals Private Limited, Nashik.

Standard Preparation: Transfer accurately weighed 500 mg of Isopropyl alcohol and 60 mg of Dichloromethane in 100 ml volumetric flask, containing 10 ml of diluents up to the mark and mix well. Transfer 1 ml of the obtained solution to 100 ml volumetric flask, dilute with diluent to the mark and mix well. Transfer 5 ml of the obtained solution to chromatography vial, add 1 gm of sodium sulphate and seal with septum and crimp cap.

Sample preparation: Transfer about 100 mg of powdered pellets accurately weighed to a chromatography vial, add 5 ml of diluent (Dimethyl formamide), add 1 g of sodium sulphate and seal with septum and crimp cap. Heat the sealed vial at 80°C for 40 minutes.

Chromatographic Conditions:

Instrument	Agilent 7890B (GC) & 7697A (HSS)
Column	Capillary column, 30 m X 0.53 mm coated with 3.0 µm cross-linked, 5% Phenyl-95% methyl polysiloxane. (DB – 624)
Carrier Gas	Nitrogen
Linear velocity of carrier	30 cm/sec gas
Detector	Flame ionization detector (FID)
Column temperature	35°C-maintain for 5 min, increase to 175 °C at a rate of 8°C/min then increase to 260 °C at a rate of 35°C/min - maintain for 16 min
Detector temperature	260°C
Injector temperature	200 °C
Head Space Condition	
Equilibrium temperature	80°C
Equilibrium time	40 minutes
Injection volume	1 µl
Line temperature	90 °C
Split ratio	1:20

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

In each parameter during the validation activity, standard solution will be injected as per method of analysis and system suitability parameters will be evaluated in each parameter. Under this heading, system suitability results of the validation study will summarize to prove that the system was completely suitable throughout validation activity.

Accuracy

Accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value found.

Accuracy will be conducted by spiking Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA) and Dichloromethane (DCM) in test at concentration levels between 50% to 150% of limit concentration.

Linearity

Linearity parameter of an analytical procedure is its ability to obtain test results which are directly proportionally to the concentration of analyte in the sample

Linearity shall be conducted for the IPA and DCM at concentration between 50% to 150% level of limit concentration.

Sensitivity

Detection limit and Quantitation limit will be determined for Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA) and Dichloromethane (DCM). As per ICH Q2R1 guidelines LOD and LOQ was determined by using the approach based on the Calibration Curve in which residual standard deviation of a regression line was calculated and determined the LOD and LOQ by using following formula:

$$LOD = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma / S$$

Precision

Precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogenous sample under the prescribed conditions.

Two test solutions as such and six test solutions spiked with Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA) and Dichloromethane (DCM) will be prepared.

Robustness

Parameter shall be performed by carrying out deliberate variations for following parameters. These parameters are only proposals. It can be change at the time of validation if system suitability parameters are not meeting.

Figure 2: Typical Chromatogram of Standard Solution of System Suitability

Table 1: System Suitability Test

Parameter	IPA	DCM
Retention time	4.29	4.76
Area	306542	156542
Theoretical Plates	13654	18642
Resolution	0.00	3.32
Asymmetry	1.12	1.03

Table 2: Analytical Data of Accuracy IPA

Levels	Concentration (ppm)	Weight (mg)	Area	Corrected area	% Recovery	Average Recovery
50%	24.81	102.11	182679	139598	103.9	100.7
		102.13	172578	129467	96.4	
		102.73	179935	136824	101.9	
75%	37.59	103.18	229745	186634	91.7	95.0
		103.49	237465	194354	95.5	
		100.17	242383	199272	97.9	
100%	50.12	100.56	308664	265353	97.8	98.1
		101.38	306677	263566	97.1	
		102.04	312574	269463	99.3	
125%	62.66	102.08	378781	335670	99.0	98.8
		103.41	375475	332364	98.0	
		100.29	380230	337119	99.4	
150%	75.04	100.84	440734	397623	97.9	98.4
		100.99	448136	405025	99.7	
		101.71	439860	396749	97.7	
Average					98.2	
Minimum recovery					96.4	
Maximum recovery					103.9	
SD					2.75	
% RSD					2.81	

Table 2: Analytical Data of Accuracy DCM

Levels	Concentration (ppm)	Weight (mg)	Area	Corrected area	% Recovery	Average Recovery
50%	2.98	102.13	80864	80864	104.4	105.0
		102.11	82280	82280	106.2	
		102.73	80864	80864	104.5	
75%	4.52	103.18	108091	108091	92.1	97.6
		103.49	117834	117834	100.4	
		100.17	117737	117737	100.3	
100%	6.03	100.56	153360	153360	98.0	98.4
		101.38	154722	154722	98.9	
		102.08	153993	153993	98.4	
125%	7.53	102.08	190893	190893	97.6	98.1
		103.41	189881	189881	97.1	
		100.29	195013	195013	99.7	
150%	9.02	100.84	224124	224124	95.7	97.1
		100.99	230731	230731	98.5	
		101.71	227532	227532	97.1	
Average					99.26	
Minimum recovery					92.1	
Maximum recovery					106.2	
SD					3.62	
% RSD					3.65	

Figure 3: Calibration Curve of IPA

Figure 4: Calibration Curve of DCM

Table 4: Analytical data of LOD and LOQ

Drug	LOD	LOQ
IPA	7.997 µg/mL	24.233 µg/mL
DCM	1.923 µg/mL	5.828 µg/mL

Table 5: Analytical Data of Precision Corrected Area IPA and DCM

SR. NO.	Corrected Area IPA	Corrected Area DCM
1	277039	161650
2	264171	155242
3	280742	162010
4	271104	158194
5	269879	157394
6	277450	161519
Average	273397	159335
STD	6105.6244	2796.6665
% RSD	2.2	1.8

Table 6: Analytical Data of Robustness IPA

Change in Parameter	R.T.	Area	Theoretical Plates	Asymmetry
Oven temperature – 10%	4.72	251903	14734	1.18
Oven temperature + 10%	3.92	248195	12531	1.16
Head space temperature -10%	4.72	251903	14734	1.18
Head space temperature +10%	3.92	248195	12531	1.16
Flow Rate -10%	4.26	170832	13221	1.22
Flow Rate +10%	4.30	336575	13795	1.15

Table 7: Analytical Data of Robustness DCM

Change in Parameter	R.T.	Area	Theoretical Plates	Asymmetry
Oven temperature – 10%	5.23	146639	23617	1.02
Oven temperature + 10%	4.35	142308	17506	1.04
Head space temperature -10%	5.23	146639	23617	1.02
Head space temperature +10%	4.35	142308	17506	1.04
Flow Rate -10%	4.73	112296	19332	1.04
Flow Rate +10%	4.78	180383	19688	1.08

Table 8: Residual Solvent Result

Sr. No.	Residual Solvent	Results	Acceptance Criteria
1	Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA)	415.1	NMT 5000 PPM
2	Dichloromethane (DCM)	0.0	NMT 600 PPM

Conclusion:

A reliable and sensitive gas chromatographic method was successfully developed and validated for the quantitative determination of residual solvents in Esomeprazole. The method complies with ICH guidelines and demonstrates suitability for routine quality control and regulatory compliance. It ensures that residual solvent levels remain within acceptable safety limits, thereby contributing to the safety and efficacy of the final pharmaceutical product. The developed gas chromatographic method is effective for the routine monitoring of residual solvents in esomeprazole and can be reliably implemented in pharmaceutical and quality assurance.

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